

Soluble alpha-klotho as a new indicator for autism spectrum disorder and its relation to oxidative stress

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Abstract

Protein soluble alpha-klotho (S-KLα) slows down the aging process and has multiple effects, notably on the nervous system. Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a global health issue that must be recognized, prevented, and treated. This study aimed to investigate the clinical significance of S-KLα as a novel marker for diagnosing ASD and to explore its correlation with oxidative stress. The study included children older than 2 years and younger than 16 years, comprising 100 healthy children and 100 children with ASD. Serum S-KLα levels were determined using ELISA.

Additionally, iron, uric acid, GSH, vitamin E (Vit_E), ONOO⁻, and MDA levels, as well as arylesterase activity, were measured, and statistical analyses were performed. Patients with ASD had lower serum S-KLα levels than the control group. The area under the curve (AUC) value (0.888, $p < 0.0001$ for S-KLα), with a sensitivity of 0.765 and a specificity of 0.921, indicates that S-KLα is a reliable additional predictor of ASD. Furthermore, a significant inverse correlation was found between S-KLα and MDA. In contrast, significant positive correlations were observed between serum S-KLα and iron, GSH, Vit_E, and arylesterase activity in patients with ASD. This study is the first to demonstrate that serum S-KLα could serve as a useful marker for predicting ASD. It also reveals interesting links between S-KLα and oxidative stress that could lead to new diagnostic and therapeutic approaches for ASD.

Keywords

antioxidants, glutathione, malondialdehyde, multiple logistic regression, ROC, vitamin E

Introduction

The circulating protein soluble alpha-klotho (S-KLα) is connected with the growth hormone on the same axis; it is also a longevity-related protein found in the kidney, brain, and cerebrospinal fluid, where it plays a vital role in regulating oxidative stress, inflammation, and calcium balance (Hajare et al. 2025). Klotho has emerged as an important protective factor that activates the Nrf2/ARE pathway, which enhances GSH synthesis, reduces MDA accumula-

tion, and supports antioxidant activity (Shaker et al. 2025), and thus α-klotho mitigates oxidative damage (Lindra et al. 2025). Recent evidence suggests that higher klotho levels are associated with improved cognitive function and a delay in cognitive decline, particularly in aging populations and individuals with Parkinson's disease (Zimmermann et al. 2024). Supporting this, a large systematic review and meta-analysis involving more than 6,600 participants confirmed a positive association between elevated klotho levels and improved cognitive outcomes, reinforcing its value as a

biomarker for neurocognitive health (Singh et al. 2025). Recent work also demonstrated that klotho overexpression in human cortical neurons protects against β -amyloid toxicity, underscoring its neuroprotective role in Alzheimer's disease (Shaker et al. 2025). Together, these findings highlight α -klotho as a promising biomarker and therapeutic target for neurodegenerative diseases and point to the importance of further research into its potential role in neurodevelopmental disorders such as autism spectrum disorder (ASD).

Autism spectrum disorder is a neurodevelopmental condition characterized by persistent difficulties in social communication, restricted interests, and repetitive behaviors, with wide variability in severity and support needs (Hodges et al. 2020). Recent reports estimate that approximately 1 in 31 children in the United States are diagnosed with ASD (New York Post 2025). ASD has increasingly been linked to disruptions in redox balance, with growing evidence showing that oxidative and nitrosative stress play a significant role in its pathophysiology (Bjørklund et al. 2024). Research consistently demonstrates elevated levels of malondialdehyde (MDA), a marker of lipid peroxidation, and peroxynitrite (ONOO^-), alongside reductions in reduced glutathione (GSH) and arylesterase activity. Together, these changes indicate weakened antioxidant defenses in children with ASD (Taha et al. 2022). Transition metals such as iron (Fe) and cobalt (Co) are thought to aggravate this imbalance by promoting free radical production, thereby increasing ONOO^- formation and lipid peroxidation (D'Amato et al. 2023).

The relationship between autism and klotho remains unclear, and there has been no previous research connecting the two, as far as we know. This study sought to investigate a novel perspective on soluble alpha-klotho by examining its levels as a biomarker for diagnosing ASD and assessing its correlation with oxidative stress. This approach may help improve understanding of the underlying pathophysiology and potential therapeutic approaches, in addition to identifying individuals who are at higher risk of developing the disorder.

Materials and methods

Study design

This cross-sectional analytical study was conducted in collaboration with the Autism Centers in Kurdistan, including those in Dohuk and Zakho cities, Iraq, from 1 October 2024 to 23 February 2025.

The study population consisted of children aged 2–15 years in two groups: 100 (62 boys and 38 girls) with ASD and 100 (55 boys and 45 girls) healthy controls, with no psychological or neurological disorders.

Inclusion criteria

Inclusion criteria for all participants included children older than 2 years and younger than 16 years, encompassing healthy children and those with ASD who met the behavioral assessments outlined in the American Psychiatric As-

sociation's (APA) *Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders* (DSM-5) criteria for a clinical diagnosis of autism spectrum disorder (ASD) (Wilczyński et al. 2024).

Exclusion criteria

Exclusion criteria for all participants included children with genetic diseases or intellectual disabilities, as well as those with diabetes or kidney diseases.

Study procedures

All participants underwent anthropometric measurements, including height, weight, age, sex, and family history. Information about their families was obtained by trained personnel following standardized protocols.

Venous blood samples (5 mL) were collected from all participants, separated into plain tubes for serum, centrifuged at 3000 rpm within 10 minutes, and stored at -80°C until analysis. Serum human soluble alpha-klotho (S-KLa) levels were measured using a commercial enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) kit with an assay range of 18–650 pg/mL and sensitivity of 2.2 pg/mL, following the manufacturer's protocol (Sunlong Company, China). Duplicate samples were prepared, followed by incubation, washing steps, and absorbance reading at 450 nm.

Oxidative stress markers were assessed by measuring malondialdehyde (MDA) using the thiobarbituric acid reactive substances (TBARS) method (Guidet and Shah 1989), glutathione (GSH) using Ellman's method (Sedlak and Lindsay 1968), arylesterase activity using the modified method (Allwsh and Jasim 2008), and Vit_E concentration by the Emmerie–Engel reaction (Korchazhkina et al. 2006). Peroxynitrite (ONOO^-) concentration was determined using a modified method based on nitrophenol absorbance at 412 nm (VanUffelen et al. 1998). Iron and uric acid were estimated using enzymatic colorimetric kits from Biolabo Company (France).

All measurements employed specific reagents and controlled procedures for incubation and absorbance to ensure accuracy and quality. Laboratory quality control included repeat measurements, periodic calibration, and preparation of new standard curves.

Outcome measures

Serum S-KLa estimation: In this study, the primary outcome measure was serum S-KLa levels, which were compared between patients with ASD and the control group.

Secondary outcome measures involved assessing the relationship between oxidative stress and serum S-KLa.

The aim was to identify serum S-KLa as a new biomarker in patients with ASD and to determine whether there was a significant difference in outcomes between the two groups.

Ethics review

The research protocol adhered to all ethical standards and applicable legal requirements based on the Declaration of

Helsinki, and approval to include patients was obtained from the Dohuk Directorate of Health, Kurdistan/Iraq (reference number: 2023228). All participants or their legal representatives provided informed consent.

Secrecy and privacy

The research protocol maintained the confidentiality, accuracy, and privacy of all children and their parents, ensuring protection of all data obtained from the study participants.

Data analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 28.0 and R version 4.3.0. Descriptive statistics were summarized as follows:

1. Means \pm standard deviation or medians with interquartile ranges, depending on data distribution.
2. Comparative analyses were performed using independent *t*-tests.
3. A two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and post hoc testing (Tukey HSD) were conducted to examine the main effects of the group.
4. The predictive ability of the S-KLa indicator was assessed using receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis.
5. Multiple logistic regression analysis was used to evaluate the independent association between S-KLa and ASD, adjusting for oxidative stress markers. Statistical significance was evaluated using regression coefficients, standard errors, *Z*-values, and *p*-values, with 95% confidence intervals indicating the precision of the estimates.
6. Pearson's correlation coefficient (*r*) was calculated between S-KLa and oxidative stress markers in the ASD group.
7. *P* values ≤ 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

Results

Participant characteristics

A total of 200 participants were enrolled in the study. The basic demographic characteristics of 100 healthy controls and 100 patients with autism spectrum disorder are presented in Table 1. There were no statistically significant differences between the two groups in any of the characteristics.

Table 1. Baseline characteristics of study participants.

Baseline characteristics	Control group mean \pm SD	ASD group mean \pm SD
No. of participants	100	100
Age (years)	8.5 \pm 4.2	9.3 \pm 3.5
Gender (male/female)	55/45	62/38
Weight (kg)	27.4 \pm 6.8	26.7 \pm 7.2
Height (cm)	125.4 \pm 5.7	123.5 \pm 6.2
Genetic predisposition	No	No

S-KLa levels in the serum of the study groups

Serum S-KLa levels were 133.7 \pm 32.4 pg/mL in the control group and 97.5 \pm 19.6 pg/mL in the ASD group, as shown in Table 2.

Table 2. S-KLa levels in study groups.

Parameter*	Control group	ASD group	<i>p</i> -value
S-KLa (pg/mL)	133.7 \pm 32.4	97.5 \pm 19.6	<0.001***
S-KLa (pg/mL) (median, IQR)	127.3 (98.9–171.4)	91.5 (69.2–123.8)	<0.001***

*Data presented as mean \pm SD and median (IQR). ****p* < 0.001

The ANOVA model included group as the independent variable and S-KLa level as the dependent variable. Type II sums of squares were used to compare the results between healthy controls and patients with ASD (Table 3).

Table 3. Two-way ANOVA results.

Source	Sum of squares	df	F-statistic	<i>p</i> -value (PR(>F))
C (Group)	31244.93	1.0	449.68	2.78e-46
Residual	10075.08	145.0	NaN	NaN

Post-hoc for group						
Group 1	Group 2	Mean diff	<i>p</i> -adj	Lower	Upper	Reject
Contro	Patient	-44.17	0.0	-51.48	-36.85	True

Group effect

There was a statistically significant main effect of group on S-KLa levels ($F(1, 145) = 449.68, p < 0.001$). Post hoc analysis of group comparisons revealed a significant difference between the control and patient groups, with the patient group showing lower average S-KLa levels. This finding indicates a significant reduction in S-KLa levels in patients with autism spectrum disorder compared with the control group.

The utility of the S-KLa indicator for autism spectrum disorder was further assessed using receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve analysis. Based on the area under the curve (AUC) value (0.888, $p < 0.0001$ for S-KLa), S-KLa can be considered an excellent indicator for diagnosing ASD (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. ROC curve of S-KLa for ASD prediction.

Patients at risk for ASD could be identified with a sensitivity of 0.765 and a specificity of 0.921 when their serum S-KLa levels were below 120 pg/mL, which is the cut-off value, as illustrated in Table 4. These findings support the strong potential of serum S-KLa as a predictive indicator in ASD risk profiling.

Table 4. ROC analysis of S-KLa in autism spectrum disorder prediction.

Area under the curve	Std. error ^a	Asymptotic sig. ^b	Asymptotic 95% confidence interval		Cut-off value	Sensitivity	Specificity
			Lower bound	Upper bound			
0.888	0.034	$P > 0.001$	0.81	0.959	120	0.765	0.921

a. Under the nonparametric assumption; b. Null hypothesis: true area = 0.5

Oxidative stress markers

Significant differences were observed in all oxidative stress markers between patients with ASD and controls (Table 5).

Table 5. Oxidative stress markers in study groups.

Parameters	Control group mean \pm SD	ASD group mean \pm SD	<i>p</i> -value
MDA (μ mol/L)	2.3 \pm 0.6	7.6 \pm 1.1	<0.001***
ONOO ⁻ (M/L)	25.1 \pm 16.9	43.5 \pm 5.2	<0.001***
Iron (μ g/dL)	83.4 \pm 18.4	60.3 \pm 23.6	<0.001***
GSH (μ mol/L)	9.6 \pm 1.5	4.7 \pm 1.8	<0.001***
Vit_E (μ mol/L)	15.7 \pm 2.1	8.1 \pm 2.5	<0.001***
Arylesterase (U/mL)	121.3 \pm 10.7	77.4 \pm 8.3	<0.001***
Uric acid (mg/dL)	4.42 \pm 1.3	3.08 \pm 0.8	<0.001***

A multiple logistic regression analysis was used to assess the independent association between S-KLa and ASD, adjusting for oxidative stress markers to determine odds ratios (ORs) for crude and adjusted values, as shown in Fig. 2 and Table 6.

Figure 2. The effect of S-KLa crude and adjusted with confounders on ASD.

The crude analysis for S-KLa showed a strong protective effect against ASD (coefficient = -3.0007 , OR = 0.050, 95% CI: 0.042–0.058, $Z = -36.87$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that higher S-KLa levels are associated with a significantly lower risk of ASD before adjusting for other

Table 6. Crude and adjusted odds ratios of S-KLa and oxidative stress indicators in relation to ASD.

Variable	Coef-ficient	Std. error	Z-value	<i>p</i> -value	Odds ratio			Model
					CI lower	CI upper		
S-KLa	-3.00	0.081	-36.87	<0.001	0.049	0.042	0.058	Crude_S_KLa
S-KLa	-2.10	0.081	-25.85	<0.001	0.121	0.103	0.143	Adjusted
Arylesterase	-0.38	0.081	-4.75	<0.001	0.678	0.578	0.796	Adjusted
ONOO ⁻	0.11	0.081	1.37	<0.17	1.118	0.953	1.311	Adjusted
Iron	-1.27	0.081	-15.61	<0.001	0.280	0.239	0.329	Adjusted
Uric acid	-1.57	0.081	-19.29	<0.001	0.207	0.177	0.243	Adjusted
GSH	-0.158	0.081	-1.94	<0.05	0.853	0.727	1.001	Adjusted
Vit_E	-0.61	0.081	-7.61	<0.001	0.537	0.458	0.630	Adjusted
MDA	0.51	0.0813	6.33	<0.001	1.674	1.427	1.964	Adjusted

variables. After adjustment for potential confounders, including oxidative stress markers, S-KLa remained significantly protective (coefficient = -2.1040 , OR = 0.122, 95% CI: 0.104–0.143, $Z = -25.85$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that each unit increase in S-KLa reduces the risk of ASD by approximately 88%. Among the other adjusted variables, arylesterase, iron, uric acid, and Vit_E showed significant protective effects (OR < 1), whereas MDA was associated with an increased risk of ASD (OR = 1.67). GSH showed a borderline protective effect (OR = 0.85, $p = 0.052$), and ONOO⁻ was not statistically significant ($p = 0.17$).

The correlation coefficient of S-KLa with oxidative stress indicators in patients with ASD is presented in Table 7, using the Pearson correlation coefficient. The results showed a significant positive correlation between S-KLa and Vit_E, iron, arylesterase, and GSH ($p < 0.001$). Conversely, there was a significant negative correlation between S-KLa and MDA levels.

Table 7. Correlation coefficient of S-KLa with oxidative stress indicators in patients with ASD.

	S-KLa	Iron	Uric acid	Vit_E	MDA	GSH	ONOO ⁻	Aryles-terase
S-KLa	R	1	0.421 ^a	0.313	0.438 ^a	-0.456 ^a	0.4190 ^a	-0.339
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.001	0.032	0.001	0.001	0.021	0.001

^a, Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). R, Pearson correlation coefficient.

Discussion

We assessed the association of alpha-klotho protein with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) in children. To our knowledge, no previous studies have investigated this association, making our study the first in this area. We observed that serum S-KLa levels in patients with ASD showed a significant decrease compared with those of healthy individuals. Lu and Hu (2016) suggested that diminished klotho levels correlate with cognitive decline, dementia, and many neurodegenerative disorders. This is due to klotho's neuroprotective capabilities, as its deficiency facilitates the onset of neurodegenerative disorders. The reason for the low klotho levels in patients with ASD may be that klotho helps control vitamin D and phosphate metabolism, according to Buchanan et al. (2020). Hyperphosphatemia is a characteristic of ASD (Raju and Saxena 2025), and the link between low klotho and hyperphos-

phatemia may be due to hyperphosphatemia leading to physiological changes. This suggests that klotho may be an essential indicator for identifying ASD.

In addition, low klotho levels may contribute to reduced defense against oxidative damage and apoptosis by taking up reactive oxygen species (ROS) and boosting antioxidant defenses (Kim et al. 2021). It can also lower oxidative stress by activating the cAMP-dependent protein kinase A (PKA) pathway, which is part of the NADPH oxidase system and a key generator of superoxide (Xu et al. 2025).

We observed increased oxidative stress in patients with ASD, as indicated by elevated MDA levels. Our results are consistent with those of Altun et al. (2018), who reported increased MDA levels in children with ASD. This supports the hypothesis that oxidative stress plays a role in the development and pathogenesis of autism, suggesting a potential link between elevated MDA and ASD severity and further reinforcing its role as a potential biomarker (Nasrallah and Alzeer 2022). In our statistical results, increased ONOO⁻ levels were observed in patients with ASD, consistent with Liu et al. (2022). This may be due to increased oxidative stress, which leads to increased formation of free radicals such as superoxide (O₂⁻) and superoxide anion, raising peroxynitrite levels in the body to harmful levels. In contrast, autism has been shown to cause oxidative damage to cells, particularly in the brain (Khan and Dewald 2025).

We observed lower iron levels in patients with ASD, aligning with Yanagimoto et al. (2020), who reported that the development of ASD was linked to iron levels. Iron is very important for behavioral, cognitive, and motor development, and low iron levels can affect these functions. Iron has also been shown to promote neurotransmitter system activity and correlate with the onset of numerous neurological and mental disorders, including autism (De Giacomo et al. 2022).

We found that children with ASD exhibited low GSH levels, which may be due to increased oxidative stress and elevated free radicals. In contrast, levels of GSH decrease, although it is an antioxidant known as the “first line of defense” against oxidative stress. It protects cells from damage caused by free radicals, supports immune system function, and is important for brain health (Davinelli et al. 2025). A recent study by Mobarakeh et al. (2025) found lower Vit_E levels in children with ASD, aligning with our findings. This may be due to its connection with higher oxidative stress, as Vit_E helps protect the brain by neutralizing harmful free radicals that can damage nerve cell membranes. Vit_E preserves healthy brain function and communication between nerve cells and works together with other antioxidants, such as vitamin C and glutathione, forming a network that defends the body against excessive oxidative damage (Pangrazzi et al. 2020).

In Paşca et al. (2006), children with ASD exhibited lower arylesterase activity, a type of paraoxonase (PON) family enzyme that helps protect against oxidative stress. The decreased activity of arylesterase may result from genetic alterations, including PON1 homocysteinylolation in

autism. Piras et al. (2021) also indicated that lower arylesterase activity reflects reduced antioxidant protection, with constantly increased lipid peroxidation and oxidative stress – a common theme in neurodevelopmental disorders. Dai et al. (2023) discovered reduced uric acid levels in individuals with ASD, aligning with our findings. This may suggest that lower uric acid levels are linked to changes in purine metabolism and higher oxidative stress, which indicates a relationship between oxidative stress and ASD. Esnafoglu and Yurdakul (2023) noted reduced uric acid levels in individuals with hyperactivity, attention deficit disorder, and ASD, suggesting that uric acid may have a pathophysiological role in these conditions.

We found an inverse relationship between serum klotho and MDA levels in patients with ASD, consistent with Fu et al. (2023), who demonstrated that exogenous klotho administration reduced kidney histopathological alterations and improved renal function *in vivo*. After klotho intervention, reactive oxygen species (ROS) levels in kidney tissue and malondialdehyde (MDA) levels in serum decreased.

We also observed a positive relationship between S-KLα and iron in the ASD group. The connection between iron deficiency and klotho could lead to impaired immune and neurological function. Both act together to lower the amount of free radicals in the body. When oxidative stress levels increase in children with ASD (Chen et al. 2022), klotho may affect iron regulation. The opposite may also be true, especially in those with chronic kidney disease (CKD) and anemia (Xu et al. 2017). The correlation between S-KLα and GSH may relate to findings from Diansa et al. (2020), who provided initial evidence that kidney injury resulting from klotho deficiency may be partially linked to the downregulation of glutathione reductase expression.

The results showed a significant positive correlation between S-KLα and Vit_E, possibly because klotho reduces oxidative stress while Vit_E, as an antioxidant, increases klotho expression and function to protect cells from oxidative damage (Xuan et al. 2016). This creates a synergistic relationship in which Vit_E's antioxidant capacity helps restore and enhance klotho's protective functions, leading to greater resistance against oxidative damage. The results also revealed a significant positive correlation between S-KLα and arylesterase activity, which may occur because both contribute to reducing oxidative stress. Low α-klotho levels may lead to increased oxidative stress, which may negatively affect the activity of enzymes such as arylesterase. Therefore, there may be an indirect link between them through their combined effect on oxidative stress.

The findings are robust and largely consistent with existing literature. Antioxidant indicators (arylesterase, iron, uric acid, GSH, and Vit_E) and oxidant markers (MDA and ONOO⁻) were statistically significant in ASD. In contrast, S-KLα, as a marker of ASD and its antioxidant protective effect, has not previously been studied. We therefore suggest further studies on the complex interaction between klotho and the pathological and therapeutic

mechanisms of ASD, which may help in understanding the role of klotho and associated oxidative stress biomarkers and in developing targeted therapeutic strategies to manage ASD.

Conclusion

This is the first study to show the important role of S-KLa in identifying patients with ASD. It indicates that diminished serum S-KLa levels are a risk factor associated with ASD. Significant correlations were identified between oxidative stress indicators and S-KLa levels in patients with ASD, paving the way for future studies and suggesting mechanisms that may underlie key pathophysiological and therapeutic strategies, particularly regarding the relationship between S-KLa and Vit_E, iron, arylesterase, GSH, and MDA.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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Ethical statements

Clinical trials: Dohuk Directorate of Health, Kurdistan/ Iraq (reference number: 2023228).

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

Informed consent from the humans, donors or donors' representatives: Dohuk Directorate of Health, Kurdistan/ Iraq College of Science, University of Mosul, Mosul, Iraq.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Use of AI

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Author contributions

All authors declare that they have participated in the design, execution, and analysis of the paper, and that they have approved the final version.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text.

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